

Hyper-thermophilic anaerobic treatment of black water for recovery of nutrients and energy

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Abstract

Resource recovery from black water (BW) (human faeces, urine, toilet paper and flush water) is currently applied, but application may be limited due to the presence of human pathogens. An anaerobic digestion process of BW performed at hyper-thermophilic conditions (70 °C) is proposed as single step digestion of organic matter and hygienisation step of potential fertilizers. To our knowledge this is the first time that BW has been treated at 70 °C. The aim of this research is to develop a process that ensures COD removal by anaerobic bacteria while eliminating pathogens and recovering resources as nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium.

Keywords: Black water, hyper-thermophilic anaerobic digestion, resource recovery, source separated sanitation.

Session: Nutrient removal/recovery linked to AD

Introduction

Within the concept of new sanitation, the different sources of domestic wastewater are collected separately in order to isolate valuable resources and pollutants in a concentrated stream. Black water (BW) contains urine and faeces, which is rich in organics and nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium. In the light of closing nutrient cycles it is evident that human excreta should also be utilized as nitrogen, potassium and phosphorous source. The challenge in the application of nutrients recovered from BW is the presence of human pathogens. A single step process, so called hyper-thermophilic anaerobic digestion (HTAD), in which biological anaerobic digestion is combined with hygienisation at 70 °C is being developed. In this concept energy is recovered as methane, and the pathogen free nutrients in the side streams can be recycled in agriculture (Winker et al., 2009). To our knowledge, anaerobic digestion of BW at 70 °C has not been performed before, but anaerobic digestion of solid waste and manure have been performed successfully (Charleston, 2008 and Nozhevnikova, 1999).

Vacuum toilets which reduce the water consumption per flush are applied to obtain a highly concentrated BW stream. This results in a stream with high COD (Table 1.1), which is thus suitable for high rate anaerobic treatment, such as HTAD. Furthermore, potentially a high concentration of nitrogen and phosphorous is present in BW.

Table 1.1 Theoretical composition of BW collected with ultra-low flush volume vacuum toilets, adapted from previous studies and applied on a pilot site in Sneek, The Netherlands (Kujawa-Roeleveld and Zeeman, 2006 and Zeeman et al., 2008).

Parameter	Unit	Calculated composition of concentrated BW
# users		32 houses, 96 users
Volume	L/p/d	3.5
CODt	gCOD/L	25.7
VFA	gCOD/L	2.8
TS	g/L	20
TN	gN/L	4.1
NH ₄ -N	gN/L	3.0
Total P	gP/L	0.6
Potassium	gK/L	1.1

Materials and methods

Concentrated BW (20 gCOD/L), collected with aforementioned vacuum toilets, is treated in a 1L upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor (UASB) which is heated through a water mantle. The reactor is inoculated with sludge from a non-optimized reactor running at 70 °C. The organic loading rate fluctuates between 3 and 5 gCOD/l/d. The BW is fed intermittently in order to have a hydraulic retention time of 4 days. The reactor was operated for 160 days.

Gas Chromatography (GC01,USA) and a flame ionization detector (FID) were used to analyse alcohols and volatile fatty acids. Biogas was also analysed with gas chromatography (Shimadzu GC-2010, Japan) with thermal conductivity detection (TCD). The gas production was quantified with a μ FLOW meter (Bioprocess Control). The COD concentration was measured with Hach-Lange cuvette tests. Soluble COD was determined after 10 minutes of centrifugation at 10.000 rpm and filtration over a 0.45 μ m filter.

Results

The COD balance of the UASB reactor is shown in Figure 1.1. The influent is mainly suspended solids (ss) or colloidal (col) COD (70%). In the effluent the COD_{ss/col} decreased to 1.8 gCOD/d. Methane production accounts for 1.1 gCOD/d, which is roughly 20% of the total COD in the influent. The big fraction of COD_{ss/col} still present in the effluent indicates incomplete hydrolysis of the BW. Therefore also only low methane production efficiency is reached.

Figure 1.1 COD balance (g COD/d) for UASB treating BW at 70 °C

Conclusion and discussion

Experiments have shown that BW can be treated at hyper-thermophilic conditions, although methane production efficiency still requires optimisation. The theoretical concentrations of nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium are 4, 0.6 and 1 g/L respectively. Future studies will have to show whether efficient and safe recovery of these nutrients can be achieved.

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